

Sociodemographic Characteristics of Hypertensive Pregnant Women in a Tertiary Care Hospital of Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy are among the leading causes of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide. Sociodemographic and obstetric factors may influence the occurrence and severity of these disorders, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. Aim of the study: To evaluate the sociodemographic and clinical characteristics of hypertensive pregnant women and determine factors associated with severe hypertensive disorders in a tertiary care hospital of Bangladesh. **Methods & Materials:** This cross-sectional descriptive study was conducted at Mymensingh Medical College Hospital, Bangladesh, from January 2025 to December 2025. A total of 385 hypertensive pregnant women aged ≥ 18 years were enrolled using purposive sampling. Data on sociodemographic characteristics, family history, obstetric profile, and types of hypertensive disorders were collected through interviews and medical record reviews. Participants were categorized into severe and non-severe hypertensive disorder groups. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 26.0, and associations were assessed by the chi-square test, considering $p < 0.05$ as statistically significant. **Result:** The mean age of participants was 30.6 ± 7.3 years. Most women were aged 26–35 years (41.3%), overweight (41.0%), rural residents (55.6%), and housewives (71.7%). Multigravida women constituted 67.8%, and 46.8% were in the third trimester. Preeclampsia was the most common hypertensive disorder (35.3%), followed by gestational hypertension (23.4%) and eclampsia (19.0%). Severe hypertensive disorders were significantly associated with age ($p=0.021$), BMI ($p=0.008$), residence ($p=0.034$), educational status ($p=0.041$), monthly family income ($p=0.015$), family type ($p=0.047$), and family history of hypertension ($p=0.002$). **Conclusion:** Preeclampsia was the predominant hypertensive disorder among pregnant women. Several sociodemographic and familial factors were significantly associated with severe disease. Identification of high-risk women and strengthening antenatal care may improve maternal and fetal outcomes.

Keywords: Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy; Preeclampsia; Sociodemographic characteristics; Pregnancy-induced hypertension; Maternal health; Bangladesh.

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INTRODUCTION

Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy represent one of the most common medical complications affecting pregnant women and remain a major cause of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide [1]. These disorders include chronic hypertension, gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, and eclampsia, and are estimated to complicate approximately 5–10% of all pregnancies [2]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), hypertensive disorders account for a substantial proportion of maternal deaths globally, particularly in low- and middle-income countries, where access to timely diagnosis and appropriate management may be limited [3]. In addition to maternal complications such as cerebrovascular accidents, acute kidney injury, placental abruption, disseminated intravascular coagulation, and progression to eclampsia, these disorders are associated with adverse fetal outcomes including intrauterine growth restriction, low birth weight, prematurity, and increased perinatal

mortality [4,5]. Consequently, effective management of hypertension during pregnancy is essential to optimize maternal and fetal health outcomes [6]. Pharmacological management plays a crucial role in controlling blood pressure and preventing complications associated with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. However, prescribing medications during pregnancy presents unique challenges because treatment decisions must balance maternal benefits against potential risks to the developing fetus [7]. Several antihypertensive agents are considered relatively safe and effective during pregnancy. International guidelines recommend methyldopa, labetalol, and calcium channel blockers such as nifedipine as first-line therapeutic options because of their established safety profiles and favorable maternal-fetal outcomes [8]. In contrast, angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors and angiotensin receptor blockers are contraindicated during pregnancy due to their association with congenital malformations, fetal renal dysfunction,

oligohydramnios, and neonatal complications [9]. The choice of antihypertensive therapy is influenced by several factors, including the type and severity of hypertension, gestational age, associated comorbidities, physician preferences, and institutional treatment protocols [6]. Drug utilization research has emerged as an important tool for evaluating prescribing practices and promoting rational use of medicines. Prescribing pattern studies provide valuable information regarding the selection, frequency, combinations, and appropriateness of medications used in clinical practice. Such studies are particularly important in pregnant women because irrational or inappropriate prescribing may expose both mother and fetus to unnecessary risks. Furthermore, assessment of prescribing practices helps determine adherence to national and international treatment guidelines and identifies areas requiring intervention to improve the quality of healthcare delivery [10,11]. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy remain an important public health problem

in Bangladesh and contribute significantly to maternal morbidity and mortality [12]. Despite the widespread use of antihypertensive medications in pregnant women, there is limited information regarding the prevailing prescribing patterns and the extent to which current practices conform to recommended guidelines in Bangladesh [13]. Understanding the utilization pattern of antihypertensive drugs is essential for ensuring safe, effective, and evidence-based treatment. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the prescribing pattern of antihypertensive drugs among pregnant women attending a tertiary care teaching hospital in Bangladesh and to provide baseline information that may contribute to optimizing therapeutic practices and improving maternal healthcare services.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This cross-sectional descriptive observational study was conducted at the Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics in collaboration with the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Mymensingh Medical College, Bangladesh. The study was carried out over a one-year period from January 2025 to December 2025 among hypertensive pregnant women attending the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology of Mymensingh Medical College Hospital. A purposive sampling technique was employed, and a total of 385 hypertensive pregnant women were enrolled consecutively according to the eligibility criteria.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Pregnant women aged 18 years or above.
- Pregnant women diagnosed with hypertensive disorders, including gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia, chronic

hypertension, or superimposed preeclampsia.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Pregnant women with pre-existing severe systemic illnesses unrelated to hypertensive disorders.
- Severely ill pregnant women unable to participate in the interview.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval for the study was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Mymensingh Medical College, Bangladesh (Memo No. MMC/IRB/2025/787; Date: 26 June 2025). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants prior to data collection. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were strictly maintained throughout the study.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a pretested structured questionnaire through face-to-face interviews and review of medical records. Sociodemographic information including age, body mass index (BMI), residence, educational status, occupation, monthly family income, and family type was recorded. Information regarding family history of hypertension and diabetes, previous history of hypertension during pregnancy, obstetric characteristics (gravidity, trimester, history of abortion, cesarean section, and preeclampsia), and the type of hypertensive disorder was also obtained. BMI was calculated as weight in kilograms divided by the square of height in meters (kg/m^2) and categorized as normal, overweight, and obese according to standard classifications.

Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy were classified into gestational hypertension, preeclampsia, eclampsia,

chronic hypertension, and superimposed preeclampsia based on established obstetric guidelines. For analytical purposes, participants were further categorized into severe and non-severe hypertensive disorder groups according to the severity of their clinical presentation and diagnostic criteria.

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered, cleaned, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26.0. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (SD), whereas categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The chi-square test was used to determine the association between sociodemographic and clinical variables and the severity of hypertensive disorders. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. The findings were presented in tables according to the objectives of the study.

RESULT

A total of 385 hypertensive pregnant women were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 30.6 ± 7.3 years. Most women belonged to the 26–35 years age group (41.30%), followed by 18–25 years (30.91%) and 36–45 years (27.79%). Regarding nutritional status, 41.04% were overweight and 37.66% were obese, whereas only 21.30% had normal BMI. More than half of the participants were from rural areas (55.58%). In terms of educational status, the majority had completed SSC level education (36.88%), followed by below SSC (26.75%) and HSC (19.22%). Most participants were housewives (71.69%), and 40.52% had a monthly family income of BDT 15,000–30,000. Nuclear families accounted for 60.26% of the study population (Table I).

Table I

Sociodemographic characteristics of hypertensive pregnant women ($n=385$).

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
18–25	119	30.91
26–35	159	41.30
36–45	107	27.79
Mean \pm SD		30.6 ± 7.3
BMI (kg/m^2)		
Normal	82	21.30
Overweight	158	41.04
Obese	145	37.66
Residence		
Rural	214	55.58
Urban	171	44.42
Educational status		
No formal education	40	10.39
Below SSC	103	26.75
SSC	142	36.88
HSC	74	19.22

Graduate	26	6.75
Occupation		
Housewife	276	71.69
Service holder	45	11.69
Business	37	9.61
Student	27	7.01
Monthly family income (BDT)		
<15,000	105	27.27
15,000–30,000	156	40.52
>30,000	124	32.21
Family type		
Nuclear	232	60.26
Joint	153	39.74

Regarding family and medical history, 42.86% of women had a family history of hypertension, while 18.18% reported a family history of diabetes. Previous hypertension during pregnancy was present in 24.68% of the participants, whereas 75.32% had no such history (Table II).

Table II
Family and medical history of the study population (n=385).

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Family history of hypertension		
Yes	165	42.86
No	220	57.14
Family history of diabetes		
Yes	70	18.18
No	315	81.82
Previous history of hypertension in pregnancy		
Yes	95	24.68
No	290	75.32

With respect to obstetric characteristics, multigravida women constituted 67.79% of the participants, compared with 32.21% primigravida. Nearly half of the women were in the third trimester (46.75%), followed by the second trimester (44.16%) and first trimester (9.09%). A history of abortion and previous cesarean section was reported by 19.48% and 23.90% of participants, respectively. Additionally, 34.29% had a previous history of preeclampsia (Table III).

Table III
Obstetric characteristics of participants (n=385).

Variables	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gravida		
Primigravida	124	32.21
Multigravida	261	67.79
Trimester		
First	35	9.09
Second	170	44.16
Third	180	46.75
History of abortion		
Yes	75	19.48
No	310	80.52
History of cesarean section		
Yes	92	23.90
No	293	76.10
History of pre-eclampsia		
Yes	132	34.29
No	253	65.71

Among the different hypertensive disorders during pregnancy, preeclampsia was the most common diagnosis, affecting 35.32% of participants, followed by gestational hypertension (23.38%) and eclampsia (18.96%). Chronic hypertension and superimposed preeclampsia accounted for 11.95% and 10.39% of cases, respectively (Table IV).

Table IV
Types of hypertensive disorders during pregnancy (n=385).

Hypertensive disorder	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gestational hypertension	90	23.38
Preeclampsia	136	35.32
Eclampsia	73	18.96
Chronic hypertension	46	11.95
Superimposed preeclampsia	40	10.39

Out of 385 women, 113 had severe hypertensive disorders and 272 had non-severe disease. Significant associations were observed between severity of hypertensive disorders and age (p=0.021), BMI (p=0.008), residence (p=0.034), educational status (p=0.041), monthly family income (p=0.015), family type

(p=0.047), and family history of hypertension (p=0.002). Severe disease was more frequent among women aged 36–45 years (35.40%), those who were obese (50.44%), rural residents (63.72%), women with lower educational attainment, those with monthly family income below BDT 15,000 (37.17%), participants from joint

families (46.90%), and those with a positive family history of hypertension (57.52%). However, occupation was not significantly associated with disease severity (p=0.287) (Table V).

Table V
Association of sociodemographic factors with severe hypertensive disorders among hypertensive pregnant women (n=385).

Variables	Severe Hypertensive Disorders (n=113)		Non-severe Hypertensive Disorders (n=272)		p-value
	n	%	n	%	
Age (years)					
18–25	28	24.78	91	33.46	
26–35	45	39.82	114	41.91	0.021
36–45	40	35.40	67	24.63	
BMI (kg/m ²)					
Normal	14	12.39	68	25.00	
Overweight	42	37.17	116	42.65	0.008
Obese	57	50.44	88	32.35	
Residence					
Rural	72	63.72	142	52.21	0.034
Urban	41	36.28	130	47.79	
Educational status					
No formal education	18	15.93	22	8.09	
Below SSC	38	33.63	65	23.90	
SSC	36	31.86	106	38.97	0.041
HSC	16	14.16	58	21.32	
Graduate	5	4.42	21	7.72	
Occupation					
Housewife	87	76.99	189	69.49	
Service holder	10	8.85	35	12.87	
Business	9	7.96	28	10.29	0.287
Student	7	6.19	20	7.35	
Monthly family income (BDT)					
<15,000	42	37.17	63	23.16	
15,000–30,000	45	39.82	111	40.81	0.015
>30,000	26	23.01	98	36.03	
Family type					
Nuclear	60	53.10	172	63.24	0.047
Joint	53	46.90	100	36.76	
Family history of hypertension					
Yes	65	57.52	100	36.76	0.002
No	48	42.48	172	63.24	

DISCUSSION

Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) remain among the leading causes of maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality worldwide [14]. In the present study, 385 hypertensive pregnant women were evaluated to determine their sociodemographic and clinical characteristics and to identify factors associated with severe disease. The mean age of the participants was 30.6±7.3 years, and the majority (41.30%) belonged to the

26–35 years age group, followed by 18–25 years (30.91%) and 36–45 years (27.79%). Similar age distributions have been reported by Bilano et al., who found that HDP occurs predominantly among women in their reproductive years, with advanced maternal age increasing the risk of complications. Women aged 36–45 years accounted for 35.40% of severe cases in our study compared with 24.63% among non-severe cases, and age was significantly associated with disease severity (p=0.021). This

finding supports previous reports demonstrating that maternal age above 35 years is an important risk factor for severe preeclampsia and adverse obstetric outcomes [15,16]. A high prevalence of overweight and obesity was observed in the present study. Among all participants, 41.04% were overweight and 37.66% were obese, whereas only 21.30% had normal BMI. Obesity was particularly common among women with severe hypertensive disorders, affecting 50.4% of severe cases

compared with 32.35% of non-severe cases ($p=0.008$). Similar findings have been reported by Poorolajal et al., whose meta-analysis demonstrated obesity as one of the strongest predictors of preeclampsia [17]. More than half of the study population (55.58%) originated from rural areas. Rural women constituted 63.72% of severe cases compared with 52.2% of non-severe cases, and residence showed a significant association with disease severity ($p=0.034$). Similar observations have been reported from studies in Ethiopia, and Nigeria, where women living in rural areas experienced delayed diagnosis and limited access to specialized maternal healthcare services. These disparities may contribute to disease progression and poorer maternal outcomes [18,19]. Educational attainment was generally low among the participants. Approximately 10.39% had no formal education, 26.75% had education below SSC level, and only 6.75% were graduates. Women with no formal education represented 15.93% of severe cases compared with 8.09% of non-severe cases, whereas graduates constituted only 4.42% of severe cases. Educational status showed a statistically significant association with severity ($p=0.041$). Similar findings have been reported by Raatikainen et al., who demonstrated that lower educational status and reduced health awareness adversely affect antenatal care utilization and pregnancy outcomes [20]. The majority of participants (71.69%) were housewives, while service holders, businesswomen, and students comprised 11.69%, 9.61%, and 7.01%, respectively. Although housewives accounted for 76.99% of severe cases, occupation was not significantly associated with severity ($p=0.287$). Comparable findings have been reported in several studies, suggesting that occupation itself may not independently influence disease progression after accounting for socioeconomic status and educational background [21]. Regarding economic status, 40.52% of women belonged to families with monthly incomes between BDT 15,000 and 30,000, whereas 27.27% had monthly incomes below BDT 15,000. Women from lower-income families constituted 37.17% of severe cases compared with 23.16% of non-severe cases, and monthly family income was significantly associated with severe disease ($p=0.015$). Similar observations have been reported in previous studies, where socioeconomic deprivation has been linked to inadequate nutrition, poor healthcare access, and delayed treatment seeking [22]. A family history of hypertension was present in 42.86% of participants and was significantly associated with severe disease. Among women with severe hypertensive disorders, 57.52% had a positive family history compared with 36.76% of non-severe cases ($p=0.002$). Similar findings

have been reported by Ness et al., who identified hereditary predisposition as an important determinant of preeclampsia. Genetic susceptibility and shared environmental factors may contribute to this increased risk [23]. Regarding obstetric characteristics, 67.8% of women were multigravida and 32.21% were primigravida. Nearly half of the participants (46.75%) were in the third trimester, while 44.16% were in the second trimester. A history of abortion was reported by 19.48%, previous cesarean section by 23.90%, and previous preeclampsia by 34.29%. Similar findings have been described by Cho et al., who reported that women with previous hypertensive disorders remain at increased risk of recurrence during subsequent pregnancies. The predominance of women in the third trimester reflects the fact that hypertensive disorders frequently manifest after 20 weeks of gestation and become clinically more apparent in late pregnancy [24]. Among the different types of hypertensive disorders, preeclampsia was the most common diagnosis, accounting for 35.32% of cases, followed by gestational hypertension (23.38%), eclampsia (18.96%), chronic hypertension (11.95%), and superimposed preeclampsia (10.39%). Similar distributions have been reported in studies from South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa, where preeclampsia consistently represents the largest proportion of hypertensive disorders during pregnancy [25,26]. According to the World Health Organization, preeclampsia affects approximately 2–8% of pregnancies globally and remains one of the major causes of maternal mortality [27].

LIMITATIONS

This study had several limitations. Being a single-center cross-sectional study conducted in a tertiary care hospital, the findings may not be generalizable to the entire pregnant population of Bangladesh. The purposive sampling technique may have introduced selection bias. Because of the cross-sectional design, causal relationships between sociodemographic factors and severity of hypertensive disorders could not be established. In addition, information regarding dietary habits, medication adherence, and long-term maternal and neonatal outcomes was not assessed, which might have influenced the observed associations.

CONCLUSION

Hypertensive disorders during pregnancy were predominantly observed among women aged 26–35 years, those who were overweight or obese, rural residents, and housewives. Preeclampsia emerged as the most common hypertensive disorder, followed by gestational hypertension and eclampsia. Severe hypertensive disorders

were significantly associated with advanced maternal age, obesity, rural residence, lower educational attainment, lower family income, nuclear family structure, and a positive family history of hypertension. These findings highlight the influence of sociodemographic and familial factors on disease severity among hypertensive pregnant women. Early risk stratification, strengthened antenatal surveillance, and targeted interventions focusing on vulnerable populations may contribute to reducing maternal and perinatal complications and improving pregnancy outcomes in Bangladesh.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee.

REFERENCES

1. Mammaro A, Carrara S, Cavaliere A, Ermito S, Dinatale A, Pappalardo EM, Militello M, Pedata R. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. *Journal of prenatal medicine*. 2009 Jan;3(1):1.
2. Hutcheon JA, Lisonkova S, Joseph KS. Epidemiology of pre-eclampsia and the other hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. *Best practice & research Clinical obstetrics & gynaecology*. 2011 Aug 1;25(4):391-403.
3. Jiang L, Tang K, Magee LA, von Dadelszen P, Ekeroma A, Li X, Zhang E, Bhutta ZA. A global view of hypertensive disorders and diabetes mellitus during pregnancy. *Nature Reviews Endocrinology*. 2022 Dec;18(12):760-75.
4. Castro LC. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. *Hacker & Moore's Essentials of Obstetrics and Gynecology E-Book*. 2009 Mar 11:173.
5. Vats K, Paul M. Study of fetal outcome in hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in a tertiary care maternity hospital of Delhi. *Int J Reprod Contracept Obstet Gynecol*. 2016 Nov 1;5(11):3773-7.
6. Townsend R, O'Brien P, Khalil A. Current best practice in the management of hypertensive disorders in pregnancy. *Integrated blood pressure control*. 2016 Jul 27:79-94.
7. Wu P, Green M, Myers JE. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. *Bmj*. 2023 Jun 30;381.
8. Cífková R. Hypertension in pregnancy: a diagnostic and therapeutic overview. *High Blood Pressure & Cardiovascular Prevention*. 2023 Jun 13;30(4):289.
9. Cooper WO, Hernandez-Diaz S, Arbogast PG, Dudley JA, Dyer S, Gideon PS, Hall K, Ray WA. Major congenital malformations after first-trimester exposure to ACE inhibitors. *New England Journal of Medicine*. 2006 Jun 8;354(23):2443-51.

10. Sajith M, Nimbargi V, Modi A, Sumariya R, Pawar A. Incidence of pregnancy induced hypertension and prescription pattern of antihypertensive drugs in pregnancy. *Int J Pharma Sci Res.* 2014;23(3):4.
11. Podymow T, August P. Update on the use of antihypertensive drugs in pregnancy. *Hypertension.* 2008 Apr 1;51(4):960-9.
12. Hossain SM, Sultana K, Rouf S, Akter R, Roy S, Anwar S, Kirk K, Warren CE. Hypertensive disorders in pregnancy: Assessing postnatal quality of care and outcomes for women and their infants in Bangladesh.
13. Cea Soriano L, Bateman BT, García Rodríguez LA, Hernández-Díaz S. Prescription of antihypertensive medications during pregnancy in the UK. *Pharmacoepidemiology and drug safety.* 2014 Oct;23(10):1051-8.
14. 14. World Health Organization. *WHO recommendations: drug treatment for severe hypertension in pregnancy. 1, Background.* Geneva: World Health Organization; 2018. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK535780/>
15. Tyas BD, Lestari P, Akbar MI. Maternal perinatal outcomes related to advanced maternal age in preeclampsia pregnant women. *Journal of family & reproductive health.* 2019 Dec;13(4):191.
16. Gilboa I, Kupferminc M, Schwartz A, Landsberg Ashereh Y, Yogeve Y, Rappaport Skornik A, Klieger C, Hirsch L, Rimon E. The association between advanced maternal age and the manifestations of preeclampsia with severe features. *Journal of Clinical Medicine.* 2023 Oct 16;12(20):6545.
17. Poorolajal J, Jenabi E. The association between body mass index and preeclampsia: a meta-analysis. *The Journal of Maternal-Fetal & Neonatal Medicine.* 2016 Nov 16;29(22):3670-6.
18. Okoli C, Hajizadeh M, Rahman MM, Khanam R. Geographical and socioeconomic inequalities in the utilization of maternal healthcare services in Nigeria: 2003–2017. *BMC Health Services Research.* 2020 Sep 10;20(1):849.
19. Hinkosa L, Tamene A, Gebeyehu N. Risk factors associated with hypertensive disorders in pregnancy in Nekemte referral hospital, from July 2015 to June 2017, Ethiopia: case-control study. *BMC pregnancy and childbirth.* 2020 Jan 6;20(1):16.
20. Raatikainen K, Heiskanen N, Heinonen S. Under-attending free antenatal care is associated with adverse pregnancy outcomes. *BMC public health.* 2007 Sep 27;7(1):268.
21. Belayhun Y, Kassa Y, Mekonnen N, Binu W, Tenga M, Duko B. Determinants of pregnancy-induced hypertension among mothers attending public hospitals in Wolaita Zone, South Ethiopia: findings from unmatched case-control study. *Int J Hypertens.* 2021;2021:6947499. doi:10.1155/2021/6947499. PMID: 34745658; PMCID: PMC8568511.
22. Mattsson K, Juárez S, Malmqvist E. Influence of socio-economic factors and region of birth on the risk of preeclampsia in Sweden. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health.* 2022 Mar 30;19(7):4080.
23. Ness RB, Markovic N, Bass D, Harger G, Roberts JM. Family history of hypertension, heart disease, and stroke among women who develop hypertension in pregnancy. *Obstetrics & Gynecology.* 2003 Dec 1;102(6):1366-71.
24. Cho GJ, Kim LY, Min KJ, Sung YN, Hong SC, Oh MJ, Seo HS, Kim HJ. Prior cesarean section is associated with increased preeclampsia risk in a subsequent pregnancy. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth.* 2015 Feb 13;15(1):24.
25. Hounkpatin OI, Amidou SA, Houehanou YC, Lacroix P, Preux PM, Houinato DS, Bezanahary H. Systematic review of observational studies of the impact of cardiovascular risk factors on preeclampsia in sub-saharan Africa. *BMC Pregnancy and Childbirth.* 2021 Jan 30;21(1):97.
26. Vera-Ponce VJ, Loayza-Castro JA, Ballena-Caicedo J, Valladolid-Sandoval LA, Zuzunaga-Montoya FE, Gutierrez De Carrillo CI. Global prevalence of preeclampsia, eclampsia, and HELLP syndrome: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Frontiers in reproductive health.* 2025 Nov 10;7:1706009.
27. Duley L. The global impact of pre-eclampsia and eclampsia. In *Seminars in perinatology* 2009 Jun 1 (Vol. 33, No. 3, pp. 130-137). WB Saunders.